

Werkgroep Inbedding CS in HEIs

14 januari 2025

CS-NL

Citizen Science Nederland

Hét nationale netwerk voor iedereen
die betrokken is bij participatief onderzoek

Today

Break-out session 2 – 14.00-15.00

Co-creating a vision and mission

Break-out session 3 – 15.15-16.15

Current activities at HEIs

Co-creating a vision and mission

- ❖ Capacity building for embedding CS
- ❖ Contribute to our mission and vision
 - ❖ Receive input to our agenda

Towards a joint vision & mission

- ❖ Build upon existing knowledge (e.g. INCENTIVE, TIME4CS)
 - ❖ Align with similar initiatives (UNL, ECSA)
 - ❖ Develop in co-creation with the community

Elements

- ❖ Embedding CS as the solution for the engaged university
 - ❖ Need for new paradigms in research and education (rewards, incentives, skills, mindset)
- ❖ Focus on regional impact: the university and its ecosystem
- ❖ Supporting mutual learning, capacity building and culture change; influencing policies & funding programs

Timeline

Nov – drafting elements of the vision

Mid-dec – draft text to review by WG

14 Jan – co-creation session at Networking Day CS-NL

14 Feb – publication

Mar-Apr - towards an agenda

Let's co-create!

Feedback to the draft text

Share: what's important and what do you need?

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Current activities at HEIs

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- ❖ Insights from EU projects INCENTIVE & TIME4CS; CS-NL inventory
- ❖ Members of the WG introduce CS activities at their institution (UvA, UT, ...)
- ❖ Q&A and discussion

Two EU projects to get inspiration from

TIME4CS

- ❖ Supporting sustainable Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology
- ❖ Reflection tool, webinars, case studies

INCENTIVE

- ❖ Establishing four Citizen Science hubs across Europe
- ❖ Co-creation, piloting and impact monitoring
- ❖ o/a guidelines, methodology handbook

INCENTIVE in a nutshell

INCENTIVE kicked-off in February 2021. The project aims to support 4 pilot European Universities (RPFOS) to promote Citizen Science in their settings.

In a nutshell, the project:

- Helps European universities to **understand the factors, drivers, barriers and motivations** that impact the decision of citizens, scientists and stakeholders to engage in Citizen Science, with the aim to provide the right **incentives**
- **Co-creates with citizens and representatives of local stakeholder groups the Citizen Science Hubs**, with a different scientific focus across pilot universities.
- Gathers different stakeholders from the regional ecosystems of universities to **enhance citizens' scientific literacy, co-define local problems, bridge opinions and create the space for future Citizen Science endeavours.**
- **Monitor and assess the impact that Citizen Science Hubs** will bring to society, science and economy, and ensure their sustainability after the end of the project.

TIME4CS Institutional Transformation

Based on the four dimensions of an institutional change, TIME4CS tried to understand change as a process that can be divided in at least three stages: a **beginning** of the change/transformations; **half-way** through such change; and the **Integration** of changes as a constant. Different pathways and guidelines in this sense emerged from the experiences of existing CS projects, the routes taken by Front Runners and the multiple experiences of RPOs around the world which together can provide actionable resources for researchers and organisations wanting to support the use of CS.

LESSONS LEARNED: FROM THEORY TO PRACTICE

TIME4CS

Relevance of both top-down and bottom-up approaches

Different contexts require different combinations of them

Covering different aspects of institutional change

Variety of drivers identified; 11 conditions selected in the framework of institutional change as a transformation

Importance of co-creating needs- and resources-based, Institutional Roadmaps/Action plans

Local and institutional stakeholders are key

INCENTIVE

Grounding CS in four national contexts

We faced variation in:

- 1) rules and regulations,
- 2) appreciation of researchers and
- 3) traditions of co-creation and stakeholder engagement

Institutional changes when establishing CS

Participation of citizen in science requires changes that are already happening (e.g. OS)

Cocreating CSHs by engaging the stakeholders in our ecosystem

- Include societal partners from the start
- Working in a transdisciplinary way requires time to define common ground incl values and gain trust

	Citizen Science		
	Projects	Strategy	Infrastructure
Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA)			
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU)	✓		Knowledge Coud & Future Lab
Universiteit Leiden (UL)	✓		C.S. Lab
Technische Universiteit Delft (TU Delft)	✓	✓	
Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam (EUR)	✓		
Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen (RUN)			Living Labs cooperation
Universiteit Utrecht (UU)	✓		Centrum voor Wetenschap & Cultuur + Social Impact Factory
Universiteit Twente (UT)	✓	✓	CS Hub Twente + Geographic CS + Living Labs cooperation
Technische Universiteit Eindhoven (TU/e)			Brainport
Universiteit Maastricht (UM)	✓		Care & Public Health Research Institute
Wageningen Universiteit en Research (WUR)	✓		Spotteron + Science for Nature + Living Labs cooperation
Tilburg University (TU)			Knowledge Transfer Office?
	✓		Arletta Jacobs + Forum Groningen

Plenary question: What do we need CS embedding in the HEIs in the Netherlands for?

Incentives and Recognition

Awareness

Connections with the community

Participation

A dedicated CS support function as professional support staff.

Trust

Need for structural funding and staff

Engagement and belief

Citizen Science Methods Courses/

Workshops as a part of the core curriculum

A common vocabulary

Reward public engagement by researchers

Make scientific work relevant for the broader public

More knowledge about each others work and aims so it's easier to share

Build long term partnerships in the region

Right incentives for researchers

Urgency and sense of joint strength

Research data

Research Support knows to redirect

Open up science process

Local impact/result

A clear sense of the value

Good practices and narrative

Contact with and knowledge of the local communities

Coordination of continued engagement efforts with local communities that are overasked and underdelivered

More permanent contracts

A central pool of skilled support for community building and communications in CS and PE projects, as project staff.

Equality of knowledge (citizen science vs 'traditional' science)

DESIGN LAB

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE.

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CSH Twente

De Citizen Science Hub Twente (CSHT) bevordert Citizen Science in Twente. We verzamelen kennis, onderhouden netwerken met burgers, onderzoekers en andere belanghebbenden en initiëren projecten

Focus op hubfunctie

Meerwaarde voor Twente

Inbedding bij DesignLab

Networkvorming & kennisdeling

April
1e netwerkdag

Mei
Werkbezoek Brussel

Juni
Open Huis UT

September
Samen aan de slag met
burgeronderzoek

Oktober
2e netwerkdag

Oktober
1st global CS4H conference

November
Grounding CS in Research
Institutions

November
Burgerwetenschap bij gemeenten

Governance

	S.E. WILDEVUUR (SABINE) Director of Citizen Science Hub Twente, DesignLab's Management Team Member with portfolio Citizen Science
	DR. M.M. VAN DEN BERG (MAYA) Program manager Citizen Science, focus on Program & Development
	DRS. M. DE BOER (MICHELLE) Coordinator of Citizen Science Hub Twente, focus on Support & Services
	W. KUIPERS MA MBA (WIRO) Community manager Citizen Science Hub Twente, focus on Community Engagement

Operationeel team

	BAREND VAN DER MEULEN Hoogleraar Institutionele Aspecten van het (hoger) onderwijs, Directeur CHEPS, Universiteit Twente.	+
	LIDY NOORMAN Adviseur Twentse Noabers	+
	GYULA RYCHTARSKI Businessontwikkelaar ADG	+
	JOOST KUIJPER Strateeg eenheid Economie en cultuur bij Provincie Overijssel	+

Stuurgroep

